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Demonstrating large Pit Thermal Energy Storages (PTES) and improving their components, processes, and procedures for an accelerated realisation of 100% sustainable DH networks in Europe.

D2.2 FINANCING AND ORGANISATIONAL EXPERIENCES

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Table of contents

1.	Executive summary	6
2.	Organisational structure	7
2.1	Introduction.....	7
2.2	Private model.....	8
2.3	Public model.....	9
2.4	Conclusion.....	10
3.	How to Finance PTES based on its organisational structure?	11
3.1	Focus on Equity.....	11
3.2	Focus on Debt.....	12
3.2.1	Raising debt for Private Company – Corporate vs. Project Finance.....	13
3.3	Focus on Subsidies.....	16
3.4	At EU level.....	16
3.4.1	Innovation Fund.....	16
3.4.2	Modernisation Fund.....	17
3.4.3	European Regional Development Fund (ERDF).....	19
3.4.4	Just Transition Fund.....	20
3.5	At National level.....	22
3.5.1	France.....	22
3.5.2	Denmark and Nordic Financing Solutions.....	25
3.5.3	Germany.....	28
3.5.4	Austria.....	33
3.5.5	Poland.....	34
4.	Case Studies	37
4.1	Case Study 1 : Financing of Høje Taastrup PTES.....	37
4.1.1	The Greater Copenhagen DH System and Varmelast.....	37
4.1.2	Business Models for PTES in Denmark.....	39
4.2	Case Study 2 : Financing of Hechingen PTES.....	44
4.3	Case Study 3 : Financing of Lidzbark PTES.....	46
5.	Conclusion	50
6.	Appendix	51
6.1	Program of Workshop 2.2 : Financing and Organisation.....	51

List of Tables

Table 1. Comparative Summary of Public vs Private model	10
Table 2. Comparative table of Debt raised by Public DH Company or Private Company	12
Table 3. Comparison between Corporate and Project Finance	14
Table 4. Subsidies granted to PTES Projects in Denmark	25
Table 5. Summary of the 4 Modules	31
Table 6. Funding Programs for Energy Storage Projects.....	33
Table 7. Overview of Characteristics of Business Models.....	40

List of Figures

Figure 1. Main types of Financing instruments to finance CAPEX	11
Figure 2. Corporate Finance structure	13
Figure 3. Project Finance Structure	13
Figure 4. Project Finance Structure – Different Counterparties and their relationships with the SPV.....	15
Figure 5. Subsidies for PTES Projects available at 3 levels	16
Figure 6. Modernisation Fund	
Figure 7. Just Transition Fund – Focus sector and countries	20
Figure 8. Regions covered by the JTF	
Figure 9. ADEME’s Regional agencies	22
Figure 10. Regional Funds for.....	24
Figure 11. Overview of the integrated DH System in the greater Copenhagen area	37
Figure 12. Simulated storage content over the year 2025.....	41
Figure 13. Composition of heat generation	44
Figure 14. Financial Concept of HECHINGEN PTES.....	45

Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

BEW	Bundesförderung für effiziente Wärmenetze
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
DH	District Heating
DHN	District Heating Network
EIB	European Investment Bank
EIFO	Export and Investment Fund of Denmark
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ETS	Emissions Trading System
EU	European Union
EUDP	Energy Technology Development and Demonstration Programme
GBER	General Block Exemption Regulation
GHG	GreenHouse Gas
HTF	Høje Taastrup Fjernvarme
JTF	Just Transition Fund
NCBR	National Centre for Research and Development
NEFCO	Nordic Environment Finance Corporation
NFOŚiGW	National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
PCP	Pre-Commercial Procurement
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
PTES	Pit Thermal Energy Storage
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SPV	Special Purpose Vehicle
SWH	Stadtwerke Hechingen

1. Executive summary

Given the capital-intensive nature of Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) projects and their long investment horizons, the establishment of a robust business case is a prerequisite for securing investor commitment and enabling project implementation. Without a financing strategy that is well aligned with the ownership structure and the national regulatory context, technically sound projects may fail to move beyond the development stage.

In this context, Task 2.2 of the TREASURE R&D project aims to support all demonstrators in identifying and clarifying feasible financing options and organisational models for PTES implementation. The objective is to provide a structured overview of the financing mechanisms and business models that can be mobilised under different local conditions, regulatory frameworks and stakeholder configurations.

This document presents an analysis of these financing and organisational aspects for PTES projects across diverse European contexts, drawing on both conceptual considerations and practical examples. The findings are illustrated through concrete case studies from the TREASURE demonstrators and further enriched by experience exchange among all demonstrators, including insights gathered through a dedicated common online workshop organised by Newheat on 13 November 2024 (Appendix 6.1).

2. Organisational structure

2.1 Introduction

Among the various phases of an energy project, financing is a pivotal stage that determines whether a technically viable idea can transition from development to construction. This is especially true for PTES projects, which involve high capital expenditures (CAPEX), long development cycles, and a level of technological complexity that is often unfamiliar to financial institutions. Securing adequate funding is thus a critical success factor for the completion of a project.

The responsibility for designing and managing the financing strategy lies with the project owner, whose organisational structure significantly influences funding models. Indeed, financing models differ substantially depending on whether the project is led by a private company or a public entity, as each type of organisation has different sources of capital, risk appetites, and investment horizons. Private companies generally pursue profitability and are more willing to accept higher risk levels, with investment decisions driven by short- to medium-term returns. Public entities, by contrast, focus on long-term societal value and service provision in line with national policy goals.

Additionally, it is essential to consider whether the project owner also operates the district heating network (DHN). When both roles are held by the same entity, strategic interests are fully aligned, and the PTES project can be integrated as part of a broader system rather than treated as an isolated asset. This alignment simplifies governance and risk management and can thus impact how the project will be financed.

These organisational characteristics are also tightly linked to the national infrastructure development model. In countries where infrastructure is largely market-driven, such as in France or Poland, energy projects are typically led by private actors and rely on competitive, profit-oriented financing approaches. Conversely, in countries like Germany or Denmark, the energy sector is predominantly publicly managed, with DHN and PTES projects often financed through public budgets, development banks or special credit institutions, or European structural funds.

This fundamental distinction influences how projects are structured and financed, how risks are allocated among stakeholders, and how capital is mobilised and managed throughout the lifecycle of the projects.

2.2 Private model

Several countries have adopted a private infrastructure development model, either through direct private sector participation or via public-private partnerships (PPPs). In this framework, ownership and operational responsibilities typically lie with private energy companies, infrastructure investors, or consortia established under PPP agreements. The public sector assumes only a regulatory or strategic role but does not exercise direct control over the infrastructure assets.

The success of this model relies heavily on the robustness of the business case, particularly the ability to generate long-term, stable cash flows that demonstrate financial viability without depending solely on public subsidies. While this approach presents specific financial and operational challenges, it also offers clear strategic advantages over fully public models.

One of its primary benefits is the promotion of innovation. By shifting early-stage financial risks to private entities, the model reduces fiscal pressure on public budgets. Private companies are incentivized to absorb the costs associated with the learning curve and compete to deliver cost-effective and scalable technological solutions. This competitive dynamic enables rapid advancement and broader adoption of new technologies.

Financing through private capital also limits public debt exposure and private actors can typically implement projects more swiftly than public institutions, thanks to leaner internal processes. This agility is particularly valuable in addressing urgent challenges faced with the current climate crisis, where rapid deployment is critical.

Another notable advantage is the long-term continuity of projects independently of political and electoral cycles as privately led initiatives benefit from enhanced stability and predictability, particularly when supported by strong contractual frameworks that secure revenue streams over extended periods.

However, this model is not without limitations. High return expectations may undermine the financial feasibility of certain projects, especially those lacking predictable revenue. Moreover, market-based systems are more vulnerable to fluctuations in energy prices and regulatory changes. They may also fail to attract investment in underserved regions that are less commercially attractive but still in need of infrastructure development.

In conclusion, while the private infrastructure model offers significant benefits in terms of efficiency, innovation, and speed, its success depends on favorable market conditions, regulatory stability, and the establishment of clear, robust contractual arrangements.

2.3 Public model

In countries where the public sector plays a dominant role in energy infrastructure, PTES projects are typically developed and operated by municipalities, public utilities, or regional authorities. These initiatives are often driven by long-term policy objectives such as decarbonization, energy equity, and climate resilience, rather than profitability. Public ownership facilitates strong alignment with national and local climate strategies, enabling these projects to be treated as public goods. As a result, they benefit from easier access to concessional financing, including public grants or subsidized loans from development banks or special credit institutions, co-funded from state or EU programs.

One of the key strengths of the public model lies in its ability to prioritize public value over commercial returns. Unlike private investors who must seek financial profitability to satisfy shareholders, public entities can focus on long-term societal benefits. This allows them to undertake projects that might be economically marginal but are socially or environmentally essential. For example, public funding can support the deployment of renewable energy infrastructure in remote or underserved areas, where private investment would be unlikely due to low returns.

This capacity to act beyond immediate profit motives enables the development of infrastructure even when financial profitability is limited, provided the project supports broader societal goals such as emissions reduction, local job creation, social equity, or energy security. These projects often align with national or regional policy objectives, such as decarbonization strategies or economic revitalization plans in declining industrial regions.

Moreover, public projects often benefit from higher levels of trust and legitimacy among communities. Public ownership can enhance transparency and liability, which in turn facilitates smoother permitting processes and strengthens public engagement. Local stakeholders are generally more inclined to support initiatives that are seen as serving the public interest rather than private gain, which can reduce opposition and delays. In this way, the public model can play a critical role in accelerating the energy transition while maintaining social cohesion.

However, this model is often constrained by complex administrative procedures that tend to slow down project development. Moreover, innovation and flexibility may be limited by rigid institutional structures, and projects can become vulnerable to political shifts that delay funding or disrupt decision-making.

Despite these challenges, the public infrastructure model remains well-suited for integrating PTES projects into comprehensive, publicly coordinated energy strategies. Its focus on long-term planning, policy alignment, and inclusive financing makes it a robust option in contexts where infrastructure is viewed as a public service rather than a market-driven asset.

2.4 Conclusion

TABLE 1. COMPARATIVE SUMMARY OF PUBLIC VS PRIVATE MODEL

	Private Model	Public Model
Funding Sources	Public grants, development bank loans	Private equity, commercial debt
Planning Horizon	Long-term, policy-driven	Short-to-medium term, ROI-driven
Risk Appetite	Lower (risk-averse)	Higher (but compensated by returns)
Decision Process	Bureaucratic, multi-stakeholder	Streamlined, investor-led
Innovation	Moderate (policy-oriented)	High (profit-oriented)
Typical Countries	Germany, Denmark, Austria	UK, Netherlands, France
Ownership	Municipal or state-owned	Private company or PPP
Capital Sources	Public budgets, public banks, EU funds	Private equity, commercial loans
Risk Bearing	Shared by public sector	Mostly on private developers/investors
Revenue Requirement	Low or subsidized	High, based on ROI
Focus	Public value, long-term planning	Profitability, risk-adjusted return
Flexibility	Lower, due to public processes	Higher, with faster decision-making

Both the private and public infrastructure development models offer distinct pathways for implementing projects like PTES, each with its own strengths, limitations, and strategic relevance depending on the national context. The private model will favor innovation, efficiency, and speed of execution, particularly when supported by stable regulatory frameworks and clear revenue mechanisms. However, it relies heavily on favorable market conditions and strong financial returns, which can exclude less profitable regions or socially oriented goals.

In contrast, the public model is better suited for long-term, policy-driven infrastructure planning. It allows projects to be treated as public goods and will prioritize decarbonization and energy security over profitability. While often slower and more administratively complex, it provides greater access to concessional financing and can support initiatives that may not attract private investment.

Ultimately, the decision to adopt one model over the other is largely determined by the country in which the project is developed. Established institutional frameworks, financing practices, and governance traditions vary significantly between nations and tend to shape the default approach. These established national models are often difficult to alter, meaning that infrastructure projects must align with the prevailing local norms and policy ecosystems to succeed.

3. How to Finance PTES based on its organisational structure?

PTES projects can be financed using a diverse mix of funding sources, including equity or quasi-equity instruments, debt financing from commercial banks or public financial institutions, and grants provided by EU, national, or regional bodies.

FIGURE 1. MAIN TYPES OF FINANCING INSTRUMENTS TO FINANCE CAPEX

3.1 Focus on Equity

In project financing and corporate capital structuring, three main instruments are commonly used to raise equity or quasi-equity: share capital, shareholder loans, and/or bonds—each with distinct characteristics and strategic implications.

Share capital refers to shares issued by a company and owned by its shareholders, whether listed on stock markets or held privately. These shares often grant governance rights and are remunerated through dividends, which are not guaranteed and depend on the company’s future profitability.

Shareholder loans, on the other hand, are loans provided by shareholders themselves. While they do not typically grant additional voting rights, they can carry interest—either paid periodically or capitalized—and can offer tax advantages, as the interest is often partially deductible from corporate income tax. Their repayment is flexible, with a defined maturity but no fixed amortization schedule, which allows greater financial flexibility.

Bonds are debt instruments subscribed by investors who are not necessarily shareholders. They pay a fixed interest rate at regular intervals and are usually repaid in full at a set maturity date (“bullet” repayment). Bonds can be listed or unlisted, and various forms exist, such as green bonds—used for environmentally

sustainable projects—or convertible bonds, which can be transformed into shares under certain conditions, such as default.

From a financing strategic standpoint, both shareholder loans and bonds are attractive tools for optimizing capital structure. They allow companies, particularly in the private sector, to raise funding from external investors while maintaining control over the governance, and potentially improving equity returns due to the tax-deductibility of interest.

Crowdfunding adds a complementary layer to these instruments by enabling companies to raise capital from a large number of individual investors, typically through online platforms. Crowdfunding can take the form of any of the three instruments—shares, shareholder loans, or bonds—allowing issuers to tailor the financial product to investor appetite and project needs. While often associated with early-stage or community-backed projects, crowdfunding is increasingly used in infrastructure financing, offering both visibility and diversification of funding sources.

3.2 Focus on Debt

Raising debt for District Heating (DH) projects differs significantly depending on whether the entity is publicly owned or privately operated. Public District Heating Companies, typically non-profit entities owned or backed by municipalities, benefit from preferential lending terms granted by public financial institutions. In contrast, private companies rely on commercial lenders, who assess risk based on market exposure and seek higher returns. These structural differences impact not only the cost and accessibility of debt but also the overall financing strategy and the role of public subsidies.

TABLE 2. COMPARATIVE TABLE OF DEBT RAISED BY PUBLIC DH COMPANY OR PRIVATE COMPANY

Criteria	Public DH Company	Private Company
Lender Type	Public financial institutions or development banks	Commercial banks or private lenders
Risk Assessment Basis	Linked to sovereign or municipal creditworthiness	Based on company or project-specific risk
Interest Rate	Typically favorable: [2% – 4%]	Higher: [4.5% – 6%]
Loan Maturity	Long-term: often > 30 years	Shorter: 10–20 years, based on project contracts (e.g. HPA)
Leverage Ratio	Up to 100% of CAPEX post subsidies	Typically 50% – 80% of CAPEX post subsidies
Equity Requirements	Often not required	Usually required by lenders
Repayment Structure	Flexible, often aligned with long-term public service goals	Structured with shorter tenor and a positive tail on contract life

These contrasting financing conditions explain why Public DH Companies often enjoy better borrowing terms, making it easier to fully fund capital expenditures with long-term and low-interest debt. On the other hand, private companies face stricter lending conditions, including higher interest rates, shorter maturities, and

lower debt capacity, which implies a stronger equity contribution and more sophisticated financial structuring to preserve returns. This financing gap is one of the reasons why countries relying on private infrastructure models may require a higher share of public subsidies to make some projects, such as PTES, viable.

3.2.1 Raising debt for Private Company – Corporate vs. Project Finance

When a private company considers financing a PTES project, the debt structure can generally follow one of two approaches: Corporate Finance or Project Finance, each with distinct implications depending on the company's financial profile and strategic objectives.

In a Corporate Finance structure, the company raises debt directly on its balance sheet. This approach is faster and less expensive to implement, as lenders base their credit assessment on the overall financial strength of the company rather than on the specific cash flows of the project. It is particularly suitable for companies with strong balance sheets

and stable financial performance, for which banks are willing to extend credit on favorable terms. Debt repayment is made from the company's global revenues, and lenders have full recourse to all its assets in the event of default. However, this structure can limit the company's ability to raise additional debt for future investments, as it increases its overall leverage. Furthermore, it exposes the entire company to project-specific risks, i.e. if the project underperforms, it can affect the company's broader financial health.

FIGURE 2. CORPORATE FINANCE STRUCTURE

On the other hand, Project Finance involves isolating the financing in a Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV), making it an off-balance-sheet structure. This model protects the parent company from project-specific risks, as lenders have recourse only to the project's assets and cash flows. It allows higher leverage and is particularly well-suited to long-term, capital-intensive infrastructure projects like PTES. However, it is more complex and costly to implement, requiring detailed due diligence, contractual structuring, and ongoing reporting.

FIGURE 3. PROJECT FINANCE STRUCTURE

Project Finance is generally more appropriate for independent heat producers or fast-growing private companies aiming to scale without overloading their balance sheets, while Corporate Finance is better suited to large utilities with robust financial positions and lower sensitivity to project-level risks.

TABLE 3. COMPARISON BETWEEN CORPORATE AND PROJECT FINANCE

Criteria	Corporate Finance	Project Finance
Financing Structure	On the corporate balance sheet	Via a Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV)
Recourse	Full recourse to corporate assets and revenues	Limited or no recourse beyond project assets and cash flows
Debt Repayment Source	Revenues from all business activities	Project Cash flows
Implementation Speed	Faster	Slower due to complexity and due diligence
Transaction Cost	Lower	Higher
Impact on Corporate Ratios	Affects leverage and credit rating	No direct impact (off-balance-sheet)
Risk Containment	Project risk affects the entire company	Project risk isolated from parent company
Leverage Potential	Moderate	High
Suitability	Strong corporates with stable revenues	Growing companies, independent heat producers

In a Project Finance structure, the robustness of the contractual framework is critical, as it directly underpins the financial viability of the project and the bankability of its debt. Since project finance is a non-recourse (or limited recourse) model, lenders cannot claim against the parent company's assets in case of default. Instead, their only source of repayment is the cash flow generated by the project itself. This makes deep risk analysis and effective risk allocation between different stakeholders of a project fundamental.

At the core of this setup is a Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV) — a dedicated legal entity created solely to develop, own, and operate the project. The SPV sits at the center of the financing structure, raising capital through a combination of equity, debt, and public subsidies, and entering into a suite of contractual agreements with various stakeholders. These include engineering, procurement and construction (EPC) contracts, operation and maintenance (O&M) agreement, heat supply agreement, and potentially land lease, insurance, and other service agreements.

FIGURE 4. PROJECT FINANCE STRUCTURE – DIFFERENT COUNTERPARTIES AND THEIR RELATIONSHIPS WITH THE SPV

Each contract is designed to transfer specific project risks to the counterparties best able to manage them, thereby stabilizing the SPV’s projected cash flows and enhancing lenders’ confidence. Key risks to analyze and mitigate include: counterparty risk (assessing the financial strength and track record of contractors and customers), technology risk (especially for innovative systems like PTES), construction risk (delays, cost overruns, design flaws), operational risk (underperformance, breakdowns), economic risk (inflation, interest rate fluctuations, exchange rate exposure), and regulatory or political risk (permit delays, changes in policy or taxation, nationalization, strikes, or conflict).

By structuring these risks contractually and allocating them effectively, the SPV improves the predictability of future revenues and ensures that the debt can be repaid over the project lifetime. This is essential not only for securing financing, but also for ensuring the long-term success and sustainability of the project.

3.3 Focus on Subsidies

Subsidies can be granted at three levels: European, national, and regional. At the EU level, several mechanisms are available, including the Innovation Fund managed by CINEA, as well as other funds financed by the European Investment Bank (EIB) but administered by individual Member States, which will be detailed in the following sections.

FIGURE 5. SUBSIDIES FOR PTES PROJECTS AVAILABLE AT 3 LEVELS

3.4 At EU level

3.4.1 Innovation Fund

The Innovation Fund is one of the EU’s most significant funding instruments under the 2021–2027 Multiannual Financial Framework aimed at supporting first-of-a-kind, highly innovative projects that contribute to substantial greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reductions. It targets low-carbon technologies and processes across sectors listed in Appendices I and III of the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) Directive, including carbon capture and utilization, carbon capture and storage, and energy storage. Project categories range from small-scale (EUR 2.5–20 million CAPEX) to large-scale projects exceeding EUR 100 million, as well as pilot projects focused on high-risk, early-stage technologies. The evaluation criteria include the degree of innovation, GHG emission avoidance potential, project maturity, scalability, and cost efficiency.

Grants can cover up to 60% of the relevant costs, and both single applicants and consortia are eligible. Projects are expected to be at a high technological readiness level (TRL 8–9; TRL 6–7 for pilots). The average project duration is between 3 and 14 years, with financial close typically required within 2 to 4 years from grant allocation and plant operating over 3 to 10 years, depending on the scheme.

Be aware that the application process is highly competitive—only about 25% of applications are successful—and demanding, often requiring 400–500 pages of documentation and a multidisciplinary team of 10–20 experts. Applicants should begin preparations at least six months before the submission deadline, starting with a strong business plan and feasibility study. Early registration on the EU portal, informing your National Contact Points and ministry, and securing letters of support from key stakeholders could be key for a successful application. Nearly half of failed applications are due to insufficient financial maturity, underlining the importance of robust and realistic financial planning.

The next call for projects is published in December 2025, with a total available budget of EUR 4 billion.

Link: https://ec.europa.eu/clima/eu-action/funding-climate-action/innovation-fund_en

3.4.2 Modernisation Fund

The Modernisation Fund is a key EU financial instrument aimed at supporting the energy transition and modernization of energy systems in lower-income Member States (see list of 13 countries). Managed by the EIB in collaboration with national authorities, the fund plays a crucial role in enabling a just transition, particularly for coal-reliant regions. With a total budget of €17.5 billion for the 2021–2030 period, financed through revenues from the EU ETS, the Fund supports deployment-ready projects and is not an R&D instrument.

The Fund targets both Priority and Non-Priority Areas, and this distinction has a direct impact on funding conditions.

Priority Areas include projects that are clearly aligned with the EU’s immediate climate and energy objectives. These focus on:

- Renewable energy generation (e.g., wind, solar, renewable heat)
- Energy efficiency (in buildings, industry, transport, etc.)
- Energy storage (thermal, battery, other)
- Modernization and digitalization of electricity grids
- Support for low-carbon mobility and electrification

Projects in Priority Areas can receive up to 100% of eligible costs, provided they strongly support the Member State's National Energy and Climate Plan and EU climate goals. These projects are generally fast-tracked in the selection process and do not require additional review by the Investment Committee unless exceptional issues arise.

By contrast, Non-Priority Areas include projects that may contribute to GHG emissions reductions but do so indirectly or are less aligned with core decarbonization goals such as for example, a project of retrofitting fossil fuel infrastructure to reduce emissions without integrating renewables or a project of upgrading existing transmission lines without modernizing for renewable integration.

Funding for Non-Priority projects typically covers 70–80% of eligible costs, with the remaining amount needing to come from national budgets or private co-financing. Importantly, projects in this category undergo an additional level of scrutiny. After initial national evaluation and EIB review, they must be assessed by the Investment Committee, which includes representatives from both beneficiary and non-beneficiary Member States, the European Commission, and the EIB.

Determining whether a project qualifies as Priority or Non-Priority is not always straightforward and depends on the project's degree of contribution to emission reductions and its alignment with renewable energy integration or energy efficiency improvements. This decision lies with the EIB, based on technical and financial documentation provided during the application process.

That's why applicants should clearly justify their project's contribution to Priority objectives using quantifiable indicators (e.g., expected GHG reductions, renewable capacity added, energy savings). Projects must also comply with the requirements of the ETS Directive, state aid rules, and, from January 2025, the Do No Significant Harm principle.

The application process involves several stages. First, project proponents should consult informally with national authorities to assess eligibility and alignment with the country's National Energy and Climate Plan. Following this, a formal submission is made to the national managing authority, which evaluates the project's strategic fit. Selected proposals are then forwarded to the EIB for technical and financial assessment. Non-priority projects undergo an additional review by the Investment Committee before the final decision is taken by the European Commission. Projects are evaluated based on alignment with fund objectives, technical feasibility, financial viability, environmental impact, and implementation capacity.

Applications typically range from 30 to 100 pages (including appendices) and must include a detailed project description, technical specifications, financial and implementation plans, environmental and social assessments, and monitoring strategies. The fund operates on a bi-annual cycle, with disbursements linked to the achievement of key project milestones. For applicants with PTES projects, there is high potential under the Modernisation Fund, particularly when the projects enhance energy efficiency, reduce emissions, and integrate renewable sources into heating networks and even more if they are located in Priority Areas.

3.4.3 European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)

The ERDF is a major cohesion policy instrument managed by the European Commission in partnership with regional authorities across Member States. Its primary goal is to promote economic, social, and territorial cohesion by reducing disparities between EU regions. With a substantial budget of around €200 billion for 2021–2027, the ERDF supports projects for a more competitive, greener, connected, and inclusive Europe, driving the transition towards a net-zero carbon economy and sustainable development at the local level.

ERDF funding is distributed through regional Operational Programs, which define specific priorities based on each region’s development level and needs. Eligible projects range from applied research and innovation to infrastructure and social initiatives, with support available for both small- and large-scale projects, typically lasting 2 to 3 years. All types of entities—public, private, or partnerships—can be eligible, though eligibility and co-funding rates depend on the region’s classification: less-developed regions may receive up to 85% of eligible costs, transition regions up to 60%, and more-developed regions up to 50%, with public entities generally benefiting from higher co-financing rates than private ones.

The application process begins with identifying alignment between the project and the ERDF priorities outlined in the relevant regional Operational Program. Project developers are encouraged to consult the managing authority early for guidance on eligibility, funding availability, and submission procedures. Proposals must detail the project objectives, budget, expected outcomes, and demonstrate strong alignment with regional and EU priorities.

Submitted applications are evaluated by managing authorities based on relevance, feasibility, impact, innovation, scalability, sustainability, and financial soundness. Successful projects will enter into a funding agreement and grant disbursements will follow a milestone-based system, including initial, interim, and final payments, subject to regular progress and financial reporting as well as audits.

To maximize chances of success, applicants should engage actively with managing authorities, clearly demonstrate how the project meets regional and EU goals, involve local stakeholders, and prepare complete and well-justified proposals with realistic budgets and administrative documentation. Highlighting the project’s long-term socio-economic benefits—such as job creation and regional value addition—is key for gaining support and funding.

3.4.4 Just Transition Fund

The Just Transition Fund (JTF) is a key financial instrument under the EU’s Green Deal, designed to support the regions and communities most affected by the transition to a climate-neutral economy. With a total budget of €19.2 billion for 2021–2027—supplemented by national co-financing and other EU resources—the JTF is managed by the European Commission in partnership with national and regional authorities of eligible Member States. Its primary focus is on coal and carbon-intensive regions facing significant socio-economic impacts due to the gradual phase-out of fossil fuels.

FIGURE 7. JUST TRANSITION FUND – FOCUS SECTOR AND COUNTRIES

Unlike other EU funds, the JTF does not finance large-scale energy infrastructure or R&D activities. Instead, it supports projects aimed at strengthening social, economic, and environmental resilience. Key areas of intervention include economic diversification and transformation (e.g. support for SMEs, entrepreneurship, and local innovation), job creation and workforce reskilling (including training centers and skills development programs), social support (such as improving community services and assisting vulnerable populations), environmental rehabilitation (including land restoration and pollution mitigation), small-scale renewable energy and energy efficiency initiatives, and digital transformation.

FIGURE 8. REGIONS COVERED BY THE JTF

To be eligible for JTF support, projects must be located within regions covered by an approved Territorial Just Transition Plan, which outlines the specific challenges and development priorities of each area. The fund targets a wide range of stakeholders, including public bodies, NGOs, businesses, and community groups—though exact eligibility and procedures vary across Member States. Projects typically range from €1 to €10 million and may complement funding from other sources, such as the Modernisation Fund, particularly for integrated approaches that combine infrastructure, training, and social engagement.

Source: European Commission, 2020.

Support for DH projects under the JTF can be limited as it is subject to specific conditions to ensure alignment with EU climate and energy directives. Heat production is only eligible for funding if it relies exclusively on renewable energy sources, in line with the Renewable Energy Directive (REDIII). Similarly, upgrades to DHN—such as pipe improvements—are only supported if they demonstrably lead to increased energy efficiency, as required by the Energy Efficiency Directive. Preference is given to integrated, holistic approaches that aim to fully transform DHN into energy-efficient and sustainable infrastructures compliant with EU standards. While large-scale DH infrastructure modernization may be primarily funded through instruments like the Modernisation Fund, the JTF can play a complementary role by financing associated activities. These include workforce training programmes for the O&M of modernised systems, as well as community outreach initiatives to engage local populations and ensure inclusive transitions.

To access the fund, project promoters must align their proposals with their region’s Territorial Just Transition Plan, demonstrate the relevance of the project to socio-economic transition goals. Early engagement with national managing authorities is essential, as the application procedures and funding availability differ widely between countries. The JTF is thus a critical enabler of socially balanced climate action, helping ensure that no one is left behind in the EU’s transition to net zero.

3.5.1.2 Call of tenders for thermal energy storage

Thermal storage are included in the Fonds Chaleur but are eligible only when included in the construction of a new renewable heat production facility.

- **Large Solar Thermal Systems**

The Fonds Chaleur's Call for projects targets large solar thermal power plants with a total collector surface area greater than 1,500 m², connected to DHN or businesses, and incorporating thermal storage, either short-term or medium/long-term. Eligible projects must replace fossil energy and increase the renewable energy share of the DHN to at least 65%, while covering more than 10% of the DHN's total heat demand. System sizing and modelling are required to be performed with appropriate dynamic tools at an hourly time step to ensure accuracy. Subsidies range from 15€ to 25€/MWh produced by the solar plus storage system, depending on the volume of heat generated and its use, with DHNs receiving a minimum of 15€ to 20€/MWh.

Thermal storage solutions are eligible under this call. For inter-seasonal storage, developers must provide an analysis demonstrating the solution's relevance and efficiency, along with a comparison to alternative technologies such as tank storage.

- **Heat recovery**

The Fonds Chaleur's Call for projects targets also installations for heat and/or cold recovery, either for internal use within a production site or for external use through a heating network or a nearby consumer. Eligible projects must recover more than 1 GWh per year of thermal energy in the form of heat and/or cooling. A preliminary study, such as an energy audit or feasibility study, is required to validate the project. Subsidies can cover up to 50% of the investment costs for small companies. Storage systems, including steam accumulators and hot water tanks, are also eligible as long as they are part of the overall heat recovery project, making thermal storage a supported component within this call for projects.

- **Biomass energy plant**

The Fonds Chaleur's Call for projects focuses on biomass energy installations producing over 1,200 MWh per year for public or private use, including commercial, industrial, or agricultural facilities. Eligible projects must include a preliminary study, such as an energy audit or feasibility study, and demonstrate both the economic and environmental benefits of using the biomass resource specifically for heat production rather than alternative uses. Compliance with air quality regulations is also required. Subsidies range from €1 to €21 per MWh produced, depending on the volume of heat and its application, with DHNs receiving between €4 and €21 per MWh. The use of technologies that enhance the energy and environmental performance of production equipment, such as hydraulic storage, is strongly recommended. Thermal storage systems are eligible when included in the biomass production call for projects.

3.5.1.3 Other subsidized financing support

Regional Funds for Energy Transition are public-private partnerships established by seven regional councils to support renewable energy projects. These funds collaborate with a wide range of stakeholders, including private operators, manufacturers, local authorities, farming groups, and private citizens.

For example, Terra Energies, OSER ENR, and AREC Occitanie jointly invested in four solar thermal Newheat projects.

FIGURE 10. REGIONAL FUNDS FOR ENERGY TRANSITION IN FRANCE

In addition, the ERDF provides European subsidies and loans, with 9% of its budget dedicated to energy between 2021 and 2027. During this period, €70 million will be allocated specifically to the transition of renewable energy production and distribution, represented by projects such as the creation of the Pau DHN.

3.5.1.4 Ongoing discussions for a specific subsidy scheme for PTES

There are currently two key initiatives supporting the development of specific measures for large-scale thermal energy storage (PTES). The first is the SOCOL working group (Solaire Collectif – Community Solar Projects), which focuses on advancing ADEME’s discussions regarding storage systems by providing experience feedback, as well as technical and economic assessments. This group brings together ADEME, ENERPLAN (the French association of solar energy professionals), and several French companies and suppliers specializing in thermal storage.

Separately, Task 45 of the International Energy Agency is a longer-term European initiative running until the end of 2027. This task aims to accelerate the uptake of large thermal energy storages by supporting major storage projects and generating technical deliverables to guide policy and project development across participating countries, with a particular focus on France. Participants in Task 45 include research institutes, engineering offices, and private companies collaborating on advancing the state of the art in thermal storage technologies.

So far, ADEME supports PTES projects on a case-by-case basis, with plans to potentially create a dedicated subsidy scheme in the future.

3.5.2 Denmark and Nordic Financing Solutions

In Denmark, funding opportunities for PTES projects are primarily available through national grants from the EUDP¹, which supports innovation and demonstration in renewable energy. Additional financing options may also be available through EIFO and NEFCO, which can help secure or supplement subsidized loans when needed.

3.5.2.1 Subsidies available in Denmark - EUDP

The Energy Technology Development and Demonstration Programme (EUDP) is a Danish public funding scheme, managed by the Danish Energy Agency, that supports the development and demonstration of new green energy technologies. Despite its name, it is not linked to the European Union. EUDP typically launches two funding calls per year, targeting projects led by Danish public or private organisations.

Eligible projects should demonstrate a high Technology Readiness Level (TRL 4–8), with a clear focus on environmental impact and innovation. Consortium-based applications involving multiple partners are encouraged, particularly those that include a demonstration component. Funding amounts usually range from €1 to €13 million per project, with support levels depending on the applicant’s profile².

TABLE 4. SUBSIDIES GRANTED TO PTES PROJECTS IN DENMARK

PTES project	Grant	Grant provider	Grant description	Financing
Marstal Sunstore 4	6.1 mio EUR (2012) <i>40% of the total system cost</i>	EU’s Seventh Framework Program ³	For the concept of a large-scale innovative cost efficient, and technical reliable 100% renewable energy supply system	Municipal loan (Kommune kredit ⁴)
Dronninglund	2.8 mio EUR (2014) <i>20% of the total system cost</i>	EUDP	For detailed design and for investments in PTES, piping, heat exchanger and a control system to connect the production units	
Gram	No grant			
Vojens				
Toftlund				
Høje Taastrup	1.7 mio EUR (2023) <i>17% of the PTES cost</i>	EUDP	Innovative aspects of the project	
Fyn	No grant			

¹ <https://eudp.dk/en>

² Funding rates vary based on company size and project type (e.g. 25-40% for large enterprises, often up to 90% for universities)

³ For research, technological development and demonstration. It doesn’t exist anymore

⁴ Loans from a financial institution owned by the municipality or with a guarantee from the municipality

3.5.2.2 Buyer Credit Guarantee by EIFO

The Buyer Credit Guarantee offered by EIFO⁵ (Export and Investment Fund of Denmark) is designed to support Danish exporters by enabling their international customers—such as PTES project developers—to secure financing.

EIFO is a state-backed financial institution focused on promoting Danish economic growth, exports, and sustainable investments. In this setup, a Danish or local bank provides a loan to the buyer, while EIFO issues a guarantee covering up to 95% of the loan amount⁶. This significantly reduces the lender's risk and increases the likelihood of loan approval. In the event of buyer default, EIFO compensates the bank for most of the loss.

The guarantee typically requires that:

- It helps the economic growth of Denmark & support Danish exporters
- At least 20% of the project content is supplied by Danish companies or related to Danish interests
- The loan is provided by a local bank (or a bank with local subsidiary)
- A credit assessment of the buyer is carried out
- A minimum down payment of 15% is paid
- The loan duration is shorter than 18 years

To get the guarantee, a premium must be paid, the amount of which depends on the buyer's creditworthiness, political risk of the country⁷, and loan duration. For non-EU countries like Serbia (risk class 4/7⁸), premiums for a 30 million EUR loan may range between 9–22%, while EU countries (risk class 0/7) typically benefit from lower. A premium calculator is available on EIFO's website to estimate costs for countries outside the 0/7 risk class⁹.

The bank is the one applying to get their risk covered. EIFO's support is subject to an application initiated by the bank, with an evaluation timeline of approximately 3–4 months (though the timeframe can be extended depending on the project's scale). EIFO conducts an individual assessment but also considers the bank's evaluation as part of the decision process.

3.5.2.3 Loan possibility by NEFCO

NEFCO¹⁰ (Nordic Environment Finance Corporation) is a public international financial institution owned by the Nordic countries, with a mission to scale up Nordic green technologies globally by financing Nordic SMEs.

⁵ <https://eifo.dk/>

⁶ In some exemptions, a partial loan is possible but not very usual since EIFO need to be sure the project is happening (case by case decision basis)

⁷ <https://subdomain.eifo.dk/landevurderinger>

⁸ According to EIFO

⁹ <https://subdomain.eifo.dk/en/calculate>

¹⁰ <https://www.nefco.int/>

NEFCO can provide loans of up to approximately EUR 5 million (often closer to EUR 2 million), with maturities between 5 and 10 years. A 0.5% fee is charged if the borrower does not draw the full amount of the approved loan. Unlike commercial banks, NEFCO is designed to take on higher financial risks, which often results in higher interest rates¹¹ — typically ranging from 8–12%.

A key requirement is that at least 50% of the total project cost must be financed from other sources (e.g. equity or private investors). Moreover, eligible borrowers must be SMEs based in a Nordic country (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, or Sweden).

The application process is flexible: a single Nordic SME may apply directly, a consortium of SMEs can create a SPV, or the project owner can apply in collaboration with Nordic suppliers. Each loan request is assessed individually, and the presence of a strong parent company or guarantee may help secure better loan conditions. Decisions are made on a case-by-case basis.

¹¹ NEFCO is not allowed to compete with private banks

3.5.3 Germany

Germany's funding landscape for sustainable energy projects is strongly shaped by ambitious climate goals at both the European and national levels. At the EU level, the European Green Deal sets the overarching targets of reducing GHG emissions by 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, and achieving full GHG neutrality by 2050, with a focus on increasing the share of renewable energy to at least 40% by 2030. Nationally, the German Climate Protection Act (2021) reinforces these goals by committing to climate neutrality by 2045 and a 65% GHG reduction by 2030. Instruments such as the Climate Action Plan 2050 and the Climate Action Programme 2030 aim to increase the share of renewables to 32% by 2030 and prioritize the transformation of DHNs toward renewable sources and unavoidable waste heat. This political framework creates a supportive environment for funding heat storage and renewable energy integration projects.

3.5.3.1 Municipal Directive (KRL) – Administered by BMWK

The Municipal Directive (KRL), managed by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Protection (BMWK), is a national funding program aimed at supporting municipalities in implementing climate protection measures. The program runs from 1 November 2024 to 31 December 2027 and is administered by Zukunft–Umwelt–Gesellschaft gGmbH (ZUG).

- **Objective**

The KRL program aims to assist municipalities and municipal stakeholders in both the planning and execution of climate action initiatives. Among the supported activities are climate protection consulting, energy or environmental management implementation, development of climate protection concepts, and importantly, the preparation of feasibility studies—which is especially relevant for projects such as PTES systems.

- **Eligible Applicants**

- Municipalities and municipal associations
- Municipal enterprises with at least 25% municipal ownership
- Special-purpose associations with municipal participation

- **What is Funded in regards of feasibility studies?**

The program provides support for the preparation of feasibility studies for infrastructure projects requiring engineering expertise. The goal is to prepare investment or modernization projects in a way that enables substantial GHG reductions and effective climate protection.

- **Funding Rates**

- 50% of total eligible costs
- 70% for financially weak municipalities and applicants from lignite mining regions

- **Application Process**

Applications can be submitted on a rolling basis using the easy-Online electronic system. A complete application must include a detailed project description and the completed application form.

- **Requirements for Feasibility Studies**

1. **Basic Assessment**

- Initial inventory of current systems
- Technical and organisational potential analysis for GHG reductions
- Conceptual sketches of possible mitigation measures

2. **Preliminary Planning**

- Development and evaluation of solution variants
- Assessment of GHG impact, cost-effectiveness, and legal feasibility
- Development of a preferred option

3. **Design Planning**

- Technical planning and dimensioning of the preferred solution
- Cost calculations and technology specifications

4. **Authorisation Planning**

- Development of documentation needed for permits
- Organisation and implementation of coordination process with relevant public authorities including documentation

Feasibility studies should clarify the technical and organisational options for GHG reduction and deliver the planning and documentation required to proceed with investment or procurement processes. Results must be supported by interim reports, planning documentation, and, where relevant, approval documents.

3.5.3.2 Federal subsidy for efficient heating networks (BEW) – Administered by BAFA

The Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control (BAFA) manages the BEW (Bundesförderung für effiziente Wärmenetze) program, a key national initiative supporting the construction of new heating networks with a high share of renewable energy and the decarbonisation of existing networks in Germany.

- **Objective**

The BEW takes a systemic approach, viewing the heating network as a complete energy system rather than focusing on isolated components. This means support is provided for integrated planning and investment strategies that enhance the overall energy efficiency and sustainability of the network. The program is further enhanced with the possibility of individual support measures at critical points. In addition, the BEW provides operating cost subsidies for the generation of renewable heat—specifically from solar thermal systems and electricity-driven heat pumps—when this heat is fed into both new and transformed heating networks.

- **Eligible Applicants**
 - Private companies
 - Municipalities (when active economically)
 - Municipal enterprises, companies, and special-purpose associations
 - Registered associations and cooperatives
- **What Is Funded?**

The BEW program is structured into four complementary funding modules:

1. Module 1: Transformation Plans and Feasibility Studies

Eligible are transformation plans and feasibility studies including planning according to the workphase of the HOAI 1-4 (Honorarordnung für Architekten und Ingenieure). Transformation plans should show the reconstruction of existing district heating networks to a greenhouse-gas neutral system until 2045. The funding amount is maximum 2 Million Euros per application.

2. Module 2: Systemic Investment Funding

Provides funding for the construction and conversion of new and existing networks that are supplied with at least 75% renewable energies, focusing on integrated, system-wide investment measures.

3. Module 3: Individual Measures

Supports isolated investments not previously included in a transformation plan or feasibility study but necessary for network improvement or decarbonisation.

4. Module 4: Operating Cost Support

Offers subsidies for operating costs related to renewable heat generation (e.g. solar thermal and electric heat pumps) feeding into the heating networks.

This comprehensive framework enables network operators to implement efficient, renewable-based heating infrastructures with a clear path from planning to operation. The BEW plays a central role in Germany's heat transition strategy and supports the national climate protection goals.

TABLE 5. SUMMARY OF THE 4 MODULES

Module	Scope	Eligibility Criteria	Funding Rate & Conditions	Max Funding per Application	Duration
Module 1 Transformation Plans & Feasibility Studies	Planning stage for new or existing networks	- Supply >16 buildings or >100 units- Transformation plan (for existing networks): plan to decarbonise by 2045- Feasibility study (for new networks): ≥75% RE & waste heat	- 50% of eligible expenditure	- Up to €2 million	12 + 12 months
Module 2 Systemic Investment Funding	Construction or conversion of entire networks	- Based on feasibility study (new) or transformation plan (existing)- Networks supplying >16 buildings or >100 units	- 40% of eligible expenditure - Funding limited to economic viability gap	- Up to €100 million	48 + 12 months
Module 3 Individual Measures	Specific components of existing networks	- Networks supplying >16 buildings or >100 units- Transformation plan in place- First package of measures implemented	- 40% of eligible expenditure - Funding limited to economic viability gap	- Up to €100 million	48 + 12 months
Module 4 Operating Cost Support	Renewable heat generation (OPEX)	- Solar thermal or electric heat pumps subsidised by BEW- Separate application required for each heat pump	- Solar thermal: 1 cent/kWh - Heat pump (grid electricity): max. 9.2 cent/kWh - Heat pump (RE electricity): max. 3 cent/kWh	- Up to €100 million	up to 10 years (annual payment)

3.5.3.3 Promotional loans

In Germany, PTES projects can benefit not only from direct grants but also from low-interest loans through a range of public funding programs. Two key financing instruments are offered by KfW (Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau) making large-scale thermal storage investments more financially accessible. These subsidized loans can be combined with other national or regional funding instruments, making them powerful tools for enabling the energy transition in the heating sector.

- **KfW “Renewable Energies – Standard” Program**

This program provides low-interest loans to support investments in renewable energy systems, including heat storage systems powered by renewable sources.

Eligible Applicants: Domestic and foreign private and public companies (regardless of size), municipal special-purpose associations, corporations under public law, foundations, institutions, private individuals, and non-profit entities – provided they feed in part of the generated heat.

Loan Features

- Loan Amount: Up to €150 million per project
- Financing Scope: Up to 100% of eligible investment costs
- Disbursement: Callable within 12 months in a lump sum or instalments

This loan structure is particularly suitable for large PTES installations aiming to integrate with renewable heat sources and DHNs.

- **IKK (Investment kredit für Kommunen) – Investment Loan for Municipalities**

This loan program is specifically designed to support municipal infrastructure projects, including the acquisition of land when it is integral to the investment.

Eligible Applicants: Municipalities, municipal enterprises, municipal special-purpose associations, and municipal cooperatives

Loan Features:

- For cities and municipalities: up to €1,000 per inhabitant
- For municipal associations and rural districts: up to €300 per inhabitant
- Minimum loan amount: €10 million up to 150 million per year
- Can be combined with other promotional loans

The IKK program is well-suited for municipalities undertaking long-term energy infrastructure upgrades such as PTES in DH schemes.

3.5.4 Austria

When considering energy investments in Austria, there are multiple funding opportunities available at different levels. Potential funding providers include national, regional, and local authorities, and in many cases, it is possible to combine subsidies from these various sources. However, funding is always subject to a maximum limit, which typically represents only a small portion of the total project cost. Therefore, identifying and securing suitable funding often requires close coordination with the relevant funding institutions to ensure compliance with eligibility criteria and to maximize financial support.

- **Subsidies provided by KPC at national level**

The evaluation of funding options is based on information available as of November 2024 and may be subject to change in the future.

At the national level in Austria, funding for energy storage projects is primarily available through two programs managed by the Klima-und Energiefond (Climate and Energy Fund) and processed by the KPC (Kommunalkredit Public Consulting). These programs support a range of storage technologies including large-scale and medium-scale electricity and heat storage systems. Specifically, the programs include support for heat storage facilities and the optimization of DHN, promoting system efficiency and integration of renewable energy. This national funding framework provides valuable financial assistance to develop advanced and system-beneficial energy storage solutions in Austria.

TABLE 6. FUNDING PROGRAMS FOR ENERGY STORAGE PROJECTS

Object of funding	Funding basis	Funding rate	Max. eligible
Heat storage systems: storage capacity of 250 MWh or more	environmentally relevant investment costs	max. 30 %	12 Mio. EUR funding
Electricity storage systems: net storage capacity > 1 MWh	environmentally relevant investment costs	max. 20 %	4 Mio. EUR funding

The costs of Large Scale Storage Systems Projects eligible for funding under this program include costs related to the storage system itself, such as cabling, pipework, and its integration into the existing energy system. Funding also covers expenses for charging and control management, necessary structural modifications, and planning costs, incl. other intangible services, up to 10% of the environmentally relevant investment costs.

Applications must be submitted online between September 16, 2024, and March 31, 2025, and must be filed before any irreversible financial commitments are made. Projects must be completed within 36 months of receiving funding approval however, heat storage systems receiving over 4 million euros in funding have a maximum implementation period of 60 months. Required documents for the application include an application data sheet, a detailed project description demonstrating fulfillment of criteria (such as hydraulic concepts for heat storage), estimated costs, site and layout plans, an economic efficiency calculation, and a report from the credit institution.

3.5.5 Poland

The energy transition in Poland poses a major challenge for heating companies, most of which (over 60%) rely on coal for heat production. The challenge facing the heating industry is not only to ensure a secured and continuous supply of heat to customers, but also to maintain prices that are acceptable to those customers. In addition, it should be remembered that the energy market in Poland is regulated by the Energy Regulatory Office (applies to companies with an installed capacity of over 5 MW). Tariffs in Poland are set according to the "cost plus" methodology, where "cost" refers to the costs of the company's operations, and "plus" is determined based on a Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC), as indicated by the President of the Energy Regulatory Office. When preparing the tariff, the Energy Regulatory Office may exclude some of the costs, which may result in a worse financial result for the planned investment. Within this framework, heating companies must plan their investments related to decarbonization accordingly.

There is currently a debate in Poland regarding planned programs to support DH. The Ministry of Climate and Environment (MKiŚ) takes the position that the decarbonization of DH should take place largely through its electrification. The Ministry specifies the technologies and solutions for which programs are or will be prepared, under which it will be possible to apply for funding. The implementation of these programs, the vast majority of which concern the energy transition, is supervised by the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management (NFOŚiGW).

Currently, there are no announced or planned calls for applications for co-financing of biomass-based heat sources. Investments in fossil fuel-based heat sources are not eligible for subsidies. The exception is the call for applications in the County Cogeneration program, open until the end of September, where it is possible to apply for subsidies for Combined Heat and Power Plant (CHP) using natural gas. Renewable energy sources (heat pumps, geothermal energy, solar collectors, and heat storage) were included in general in the now-completed priority program "Renewable Energy Sources as a heat source for district heating." A second call for applications is planned for December 2025, but this depends on the availability of funds. In addition, there are plans to launch a call for applications under the County Heating program, financed by the National Recovery Plan.

There is no funding dedicated to large-scale heat storage facilities under the open calls for proposals. Heat storage facilities can only be an additional element of investments in heat sources, but not an independent investment.

The maximum aid intensity for heating companies that are large enterprises is specified in the General Block Exemption Regulation (GBER) and amounts to:

- up to 45% of eligible costs if the project concerns the production of heat energy from renewable energy sources,
- up to 30% of eligible costs for CHP,

There is also the funding gap method as an alternative way of calculating the maximum public aid in accordance with the GBER (EU Commission Regulation No. 651/2014), which is usually used for projects related to the construction/expansion of heating networks.

The process of obtaining funding, as exemplified by the NFOŚiGW, is as follows:

1. A company planning to invest in a new source or solution must first familiarize itself with the requirements of the call for proposals. The expectations of the competition organizer (NFOŚiGW) are very extensive and cover many areas, e.g., a detailed description of the technology, the impact of the investment on the heating system – energy audit, confirmation of own contribution supplementing the funding, as well as proof that the company is able to maintain the planned results and indicators for a period of at least 5 years – i.e., the durability period. In addition, a description of the market is required – both in terms of competition and service recipients and its prospects, the process of obtaining the necessary certificates and administrative permits, including the right to dispose of real estate, environmental decisions, conditions for connection to the power grid, etc., as well as a presentation of the project implementation schedule together with the financial structure of the investment.

2. The next step is to prepare the required documents. Usually, the necessary documents are:

- Feasibility study – prepared using the template provided. One of the essential elements is to demonstrate that the planned solution is the most cost-effective and environmentally friendly compared to alternative technologies.

- Financial model – prepared using the template provided. Depending on the type of company submitting the application (large or SME) and the company that will implement the project, the boundary conditions for co-financing will differ. You can apply for a grant, a grant with a loan, or a grant with a financial instrument. It is necessary to demonstrate the funds to cover the own contribution, e.g., in the form of a loan commitment from a bank or funds in the company's account.

- Investment schedule - prepared using the template provided.

- Schedule for the launch of grants and loans from public funds;

- Schedule for obtaining the necessary approvals and permits – this will allow you to determine at the application stage whether the project can be completed within the specified time frame, and will also allow you to plan the work on the investment well.

- Documents concerning the company applying for funding, such as articles of association or partnership agreement, financial statements, etc.

3. Once the set of documents has been prepared, they must be submitted via the dedicated NFOŚiGW online platform. After the call for applications has closed, a two-stage evaluation process takes place:

- The first stage is a formal assessment of the application: it is verified whether all the required fields in the application have been completed and all the required documents and attachments have been attached, as well as whether they have been signed by authorized persons.

- the second stage is a substantive assessment – technical and financial: experts from the NFOŚiGW assess the application from a technical and financial point of view and, if necessary, request additional information and explanations.

At both stages of the assessment, the applicant has 5 working days to submit additional information, if requested.

4. If the application is approved, the applicant signs a co-financing agreement with the NFOŚiGW. At this stage, the investment schedule and the schedules for the launch of grants and loans are updated.

Co-financing of investments in the construction and/or modernization of heating networks is currently only possible through a financial instrument consisting of four mandatory sources of financing: grants, preferential loans, market-rate loans, and own contributions to non-eligible costs. An example of the financial structure is presented in the table below:

	Financing scheme	%
1	Grant	40.66
2	Interest-free loan	39.05
3	Market loan	20.29
Total		100.00

The table below presents an example of a financial arrangement for an investment in a renewable energy heat source, co-financed by the Modernization Fund:

No.	Financing scheme	%
1	Grant	45.00
2	Own funds	55.00
Total		100.00

4. Case Studies

4.1 Case Study 1 : Financing of Høje Taastrup PTES

4.1.1 The Greater Copenhagen DH System and Varmelast

The DH system in the Greater Copenhagen area accounts for approximately 25% of Denmark's total DH consumption. The system consists of numerous distribution networks and a transmission network that supplies heat at a higher temperature. Today's DH system is dominated by large central combined heat and power (CHP) plants based on waste and biomass:

- Four CHP plants with a total capacity of 2,050 MJ/s. These plants are owned by three different companies: Ørsted, HOFOR, and VEKS.
- Three waste-to-energy plants with a total capacity of 400 MJ/s: ARGO, Vestforbrænding, and Amager Resource Center.
- Reserve and peak-load facilities with a total capacity of 1,900 MJ/s. These are based on natural gas, with backup capacity using light fuel oil. In recent years, several electric boilers have been established for peak and reserve load purposes.
- Two heat accumulators with a combined capacity of 660 MJ/s.

CTR, HOFOR, and VEKS purchase heat from the larger production facilities. In recent years, there has been a trend toward establishing smaller local production units connected to industrial surplus heat and wastewater treatment plants.

FIGURE 11. OVERVIEW OF THE INTEGRATED DH SYSTEM IN THE GREATER COPENHAGEN AREA

The load distribution of heat production facilities in the system is managed on a daily basis and is crucial for how DH is produced within the integrated DHN. Load distribution refers to how heat production is scheduled each day to ensure it is always generated by the lowest-cost plants.

The principles for load distribution are defined by the DH companies CTR, HOFOR, and VEKS and are agreed upon with the other actors in the system. Daily load distribution is carried out by the unit Varmelast, which is jointly owned by CTR, HOFOR, and VEKS.

There are currently different types of load distribution:

- Large production facilities are centrally dispatched through Varmelast using economic optimization, which minimizes the total cost of heat and electricity production on an hourly basis.
- Certain facilities may be prioritized ahead of other large plants. Currently, this applies to waste heat based on mandatory waste incineration (priority production).
- Decentralized optimization: Individual local heat producers optimize their own production based on varying price signals, for example from the transmission company. This typically includes small producers, such as those utilizing surplus heat in local distribution networks.

The load distribution of large production plants is based on the principle of overall, cost-based optimization for both electricity and heat. Load distribution is carried out independently of billing processes (load distribution and settlement are governed by separate contract frameworks).

As part of the load distribution process, heat production plans are created at least six times per day:

- A day-ahead plan (before the electricity spot market closes)
- Five intraday adjustments (after the spot market closes), with possible additional adjustments

Load distribution is based on consumption forecasts (updated six times a day), the producers' desired production (production plans), limitations in the network and at the plants, thermal storage levels, and marginal prices submitted by producers.

Varmelast also conducts daily operational follow-ups to assess whether production is aligned with plans and how far it deviates from the optimal load distribution. Producers submit bids for heat production to Varmelast.

These bids are based on variable costs, which include:

- Fuel prices
- Plant capacities and efficiencies
- Variable O&M costs
- Energy and CO₂ taxes on heat production
- CO₂ quota costs
- Revenue forecasts from the electricity market
- Production subsidies for biomass-based electricity

When Varmelast places heat production orders with producers, it takes into account the most critical technical constraints in the DHN and at the production facilities. Varmelast also has the ability to store heat in large thermal storage units for shorter periods.

In the course of daily operations, actual conditions often develop differently than predicted in the forecasts. Therefore, the heat production plans are adjusted six times a day based on updated consumption forecasts, the published market price of electricity, and unforeseen outages at the CHP plants.

4.1.2 Business Models for PTES in Denmark

Overall, a good business model must ensure the following:

- That financing can be secured for the establishment of energy storage systems, which help reduce the cost of producing and delivering DH. Providing security for investors
- A solution that is administratively simple and efficient
- The possibility of reliable technical O&M of the facility

4.1.2.1 General analysis of different Business Models

In Denmark, existing thermal storage units are typically owned and operated by a single DH company or producer, often to integrate solar heating or optimize the operation of their own CHP plants. This is not the case in an integrated DHN like that of the Greater Copenhagen area, where thermal storage will need to be established to benefit the entire system—therefore involving multiple stakeholders.

It has been demonstrated that PTES will benefit both heat producers who buy or sell electricity—by allowing them to optimize operations based on hourly electricity price fluctuations—and DH companies and producers, by reducing reliance on expensive peak-load plants and increasing production from cheaper sources such as CHP and heat pumps. There was therefore a need to define a business model that will ensure maximum value from storage facilities in systems with multiple producers and actors.

Three Different Business Models Have Been Evaluated:

A. Commercial Model: A commercial PTES company buys and sells DH. The business case is driven by the price difference between purchase and sale, as well as payment for balancing services and reserve/peak load capacity.

B. Infrastructure (Varmelast) Model: DH companies or Varmelast establish and operate the heat storage facility. The storage is integrated into the load distribution on open and objective terms.

C. DH Company or Producer Model: A DH company or heat producer establishes and operates the storage facility. Operations are optimized to improve the company's economics, either by reducing purchase costs for consumers or by enhancing production from their own facilities.

In addition, hybrid models combining elements of models B and C have also been considered.

An overview of the models is presented in the table below.

TABLE 7. OVERVIEW OF CHARACTERISTICS OF BUSINESS MODELS¹²

Subject	Commercially	Infrastructure	Company-owned
Model Description	The PTES company buys and sells DH. The price difference between buying and selling as well as payment for regulation services and spare cargo/peak load services drives the economy.	DH companies (or Varmelast.dk) establish and operate the heat storage. The heat storage is included in the load distribution on open and objective terms.	The DH company or producer establishes and operates the heat storage. Operations optimize the company's finances for purchases to consumers or production from its own facilities.
Investment costs and operating expenses incl. losses	Covered by investor	Held by heating companies. Can be shared between actors on a pro rata basis according to utility. Can be supplemented with the sale of storage	Covered by DH company or producer
Security on investment	Uncertain – depends on price developments in the market	The Heat Supply Act allows for inclusion in the heat price	The utility is driven solely by optimizing its own plant. Can be fully or partially included in the heat price, but difficult to get good socio-economics
Responsibility for operations	Investor	DH Co.	Producer of DH Co.
Advantages	In principle, a simple investment and settlement model.	The best possible utilization of the storage, as it benefits all players. Can be approved.	Simple investment and settlement model. Easier to react to rapid fluctuations in the electricity market. Harder to get approved.
Disadvantages	Requires the establishment of an hourly market / transparent price. Considered highly risk	Difficult to determine who will benefit and thus the distribution of investment and operating costs	Sub-optimization that the storage is only used by the manufacturer in question.

4.1.2.2 Settlement of the different Business Models

The settlement model for Models A and C is, in principle, straightforward, as a single actor establishes the storage facility and secures revenue by optimizing its own facility or facilities in relation to market prices. However, Model A requires the establishment of an hourly-based market or a transparent price reference that can be used for settling the purchase and sale of heat. Such a market does not currently exist.

For Model B, the settlement is more complex, as both the investment and the resulting benefits must be distributed among multiple actors. The following types of settlement models can be considered:

- 50% paid by the DH companies, with producers covering the investment and ongoing O&M costs based on heat production per GJ of delivered heat
 - This is a simple model
 - In this case, producers would pay an annual tariff of XX DKK/GJ of heat produced to cover the investment and ongoing O&M costs

¹² Source : Ea Energy Analysis

- Does not necessarily ensure a direct 1:1 relationship between payment and operational benefit
- In this model, the investment is seen as an improvement to the overall infrastructure shared by all actors and as a development project
- This model may be directly replicable for future heat storage projects
- Payment of investment and ongoing O&M based on calculated operational benefit before project start :
 - The investment can be paid over time or as an upfront lump sum
 - O&M can be paid via an annual invoice
 - Does not necessarily ensure a direct match between estimated and realized benefits
 - Reaching consensus on expected operational benefits among all parties may be challenging
- Payment of investment and ongoing O&M based on annual calculation of the value of the storage per actor :
 - Administratively burdensome. For instance in Copenhagen it is difficult to calculate the annual value because no reference for the same period without PTES exists

4.1.2.3 Concrete Case of Høje Taastrup PTES in the Greater Copenhagen DHN

A series of analyses were conducted for the PTES project in Høje Taastrup, which served as the basis for selecting the business model for that storage. The facility was officially commissioned in 2023, but prior to its commissioning, several analyses were carried out that formed the foundation for its business case and for negotiations regarding the business model and agreements among the many parties involved in the project.

The heat storage facility in Høje Taastrup has a volume of 70,000 m³, corresponding to an energy content of 3,300 MWh at the operating temperatures in use. The storage has a charging and discharging capacity of 30 MW, which means it can be filled or emptied in 110 hours. It is charged from the transmission network and discharged to the distribution network. The storage cannot deliver heat back into the transmission network.

Model analyses showed that the storage facility will function as a weekly buffer, as illustrated in figure below.

FIGURE 12. SIMULATED STORAGE CONTENT OVER THE YEAR 2025¹³

¹³ Source: Ea Energy Analysis

The analyses showed that the value (operational benefit) of the storage is created through:

- Increased production from the most efficient available CHP and waste-to-energy plants
- Reduced peak load and bypass operation, particularly during winter
- Optimization of CHP plant operation in response to electricity prices

The value of the storage is distributed among stakeholders based on the altered load distribution and production at the plants, as well as the heat sales contracts established between producers and DH companies. Prior to the establishment of the storage facility in Høje Taastrup, it was estimated that the value of the storage (before investment costs were factored in) would be distributed among the actors as follows:

- Transmission companies (VEKS and CTR): approx. 56% of the operational benefit, due to avoided peak load
- CHP producers: approx. 28% of the benefit, due to better optimization based on electricity prices and increased heat sales
- Waste incineration plants: approx. 16% of the benefit, due to improved optimization in relation to electricity prices and increased heat delivery

Specifically, for the Høje Taastrup storage facility, the following agreements were made:

- An infrastructure model was selected (Model B described previously). All parties that receive economic benefit from the storage participate in the financing, in exchange for Høje Taastrup Fjernvarme and VEKS ensuring that the entire storage capacity is made available for daily load distribution.
- VEKS has entered into agreements with all major CHP producers, waste incineration plants, and CTR, who pay a fixed annual fee for 20 years for this availability (based on the calculated operational benefit).
- Heat producers and transmission companies contribute to the investment and operation, and 20-year agreements have been signed with all parties.
- None of the involved parties become owners of the storage facility.

More precisely, the following was agreed:

- The heat storage is owned jointly by VEKS and Høje Taastrup Fjernvarme (HTF), on a 50%/50% basis.
- Investment costs are borne equally by VEKS and HTF (50%/50%).
- VEKS purchases the right to use HTF's share of the storage capacity for 20 years by paying annual compensation for HTF not using their share of the capacity (equivalent to HTF's share of the investment).

A cooperation agreement and an operator agreement according to operation and monitoring of the storage performance have been signed between VEKS and HTF.

Income/year of the Project is calculated to 1.05 MEUR and operation costs are estimated to 0.16 MEUR/year. This results in a simple payback period of 12 years and an Internal Rate of Return of 7.5% calculated for 20 years. The lifetime for the PTES is expected to be more than 20 years.

The total investment amount was 12.04 MEUR out of which 1.34 MEUR was financed by a subsidy from EUDP as detailed below :

Activity	Investment, Mio. €
Soil expenses	0.55
Design and supervision	1.14
Storage and pumping station	6,05
Heat exchanger building	2.42
District heating pipeline	0.94
Electricity etc.	0.44
Water	0.51
Total	12.04
EUDP subsidies	1.34
Total incl. subsidies	10.70

The remaining 10.7 MEUR was financed at 100% by a loan with municipal guarantee from Kommunekredit.

KommuneKredit is a non-profit financial institution owned by all local governments in Denmark. It provides direct loans to Danish municipalities to finance infrastructure projects, as well as to Danish utilities carrying out public tasks, provided these loans are fully guaranteed by one or more local governments. During the construction phase, KommuneKredit issues a construction loan with a variable interest rate, which is then refinanced at commercial operation date by a long-term loan spanning 30 years with either fixed or floating interest rates.

A key feature of KommuneKredit's model is that all local governments are jointly and severally liable for its obligations, making its cost of funding tied to Denmark's sovereign credit rating rather than to individual projects it will finance. This joint liability and secure business structure enable KommuneKredit to maintain its credit rating to the highest level possible, equal to the credit rating of Denmark. As its credit risk is based on state risk, KommuneKredit can finance itself through bond issuances on both Danish and international capital markets, including green bonds specifically aimed at renewable energy projects such as DH, which represents about 20% of its lending portfolio. With low cost of funding, KommuneKredit can then offer loans at favorable interest rates and administration costs to finance infrastructure projects. The Danish Act on KommuneKredit restricts its lending exclusively to local governments and enterprises performing public tasks with full guarantees from local governments. This special credit institution operates within EU state aid rules, allowing it to provide financing to public entities without restrictions and to subsidize loans to other beneficiaries when aligned with state aid regulations. Loans to DH companies, which fulfill a public task in Denmark, benefit from this framework.

Danish legislation on collective heating authorizes municipalities to provide unconditional and irrevocable loan guarantees covering 100% of capital investments for DH projects, whether publicly or privately owned. This legal and financial setup enables KommuneKredit to support sustainable local infrastructure development efficiently and at competitive terms.

4.2 Case Study 2 : Financing of Hechingen PTES

The PTES in the city of Hechingen is an integral part of the Killberg IV heat supply system, which is designed to meet an annual heat demand of approximately 3.9 GWh. The system operates with temperatures of the DNH between 38°C and 68 °C and features a combination of renewable and sustainable technologies, including:

- 7,600 m² of solar thermal collectors,
- 18,000 m³ PTES,
- 500 kW thermal heat pump with a PTES as heatsource,
- 300 kW geothermal heat pump,
- 42 geothermal borehole heat exchangers with a dept of 172 m,
- two buffer storages of 105 m³ and 55 m³, and
- three 1 MW peak biogas boilers.

FIGURE 13. COMPOSITION OF HEAT GENERATION

The local utility company Stadtwerke Hechingen (SWH) owns and will operate the Killberg IV system, including the PTES. In Germany, local utility companies like SWH typically manage services such as energy (heat, gas, electricity), water supply, wastewater treatment, and public facilities, often in direct cooperation with the municipality. SWH is an “Eigenbetrieb”, meaning it is legally dependent on, but organisationally independent from, the city of Hechingen. The PTES will be installed on the “Hinter Rieb” landfill site, which is managed by another municipal company, Entsorgungsbetrieb Hechingen, also an “Eigenbetrieb” of the city. This integration of municipal resources reflects a coordinated public effort to implement innovative, low-carbon heating infrastructure.

The financing model for the PTES and the broader Killberg IV heat supply system in Hechingen is closely linked to the urban development strategy of the city. The construction area and individual building sites are owned by the city of Hechingen and are currently being marketed and sold to customers. All new buildings in the development are legally required to connect to the DNH, ensuring long-term demand for the renewable heat supplied by SWH, the municipal utility.

Customers will pay for their heat supply through a combination of fixed one-time connection fees, fixed monthly charges based on building type, and variable costs based on actual heat consumption. Although final pricing is still under development, the cost model will be calculated over a 30-year period and adjusted annually to reflect changes in operating costs such as electricity and labor.

The total investment for the heat supply system, including the PTES and DHN, is estimated at €17.5 million. This will be financed entirely through a bank loan, with no upfront equity capital, and is expected to be repaid through revenue generated from heat sales. To support the project, the BEW provides significant public subsidies. Nearly all components of the heat generation and distribution system are eligible for 40% investment funding. In addition, operational support is granted for renewable heat generation: solar thermal heat receives 1 ct€/kWh and geothermal heat receives 6.4 ct€/kWh for a period of 10 years. These subsidies play a critical role in improving the project’s financial viability and in reducing long-term heating costs for end-users.

FIGURE 14. FINANCIAL CONCEPT OF HECHINGEN PTES

4.3 Case Study 3 : Financing of Lidzbark PTES

The Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) demonstrator in Lidzbark Warmiński forms part of a broader, integrated renewable district heating installation developed as a full-scale demonstration of next-generation heating systems. The installation, commonly referred to as the “Heat Plant of the Future” (*Ciepłownia Przyszłości*), combines several complementary technologies into a single, highly integrated system optimised for high renewable energy penetration and operational flexibility.

The complete installation consists of the following main components:

- Heat pumps with a total thermal capacity of 2.6 MW
- Air-to-water heat exchangers supporting low-temperature heat recovery
- Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (BTES) comprising 300 boreholes, each with a depth of 100 m (total borehole length: 30,000 m)
- Hybrid photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) collectors with electric power of 0.2 MW
- A directly connected photovoltaic power plant with an installed capacity of 1.3 MW
- A thermal buffer storage with a volume of 100 m³

The system was designed to supply both space heating and domestic hot water to a separated district heating network serving 22 residential buildings at Osiedle Astronomów under real operating conditions. The installation represents a high level of technological integration, combining electrically driven heat production with heat pumps, renewable electricity generation, and both short- and long-term thermal storage.

Financing framework and pre-commercial procurement scheme

The Lidzbark Warmiński demonstrator was financed entirely with public funds under a pre-commercial procurement (PCP) framework managed by National Centre for Research and Development (NCBR). The project was co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) under Sub-measure 4.1.3 Innovative R&D Management Models of the Operational Programme Smart Growth 2014–2020, within the project “Increasing the Innovativeness of the Economy through the Implementation of a New Financing Model for Breakthrough R&D Projects” (Grant Agreement of 12 April 2017, No. POIR.04.01.03-00-0001/16).

The procurement procedure was launched as a dedicated PCP programme aligned with the objectives of the European Green Deal, focusing on zero-emission district heating systems based exclusively on renewable energy sources, explicitly excluding biomass combustion. NCBR launched a dedicated PCP procedure targeting innovative district heating systems based on renewable energy sources, explicitly excluding biomass combustion. The PCP framework was structured to stimulate technological innovation while limiting investment risk for public authorities and end-users.

The procurement process was divided into several successive stages:

Preliminary stage – Market dialogue

An open technical dialogue was conducted with the market, involving district heating companies, universities, research institutes, technology providers, and engineering firms. This phase aimed to identify realistic yet ambitious performance requirements for a demonstrator representing the future development pathway of the Polish district heating sector. The dialogue helped define high technical standards while ensuring technological feasibility and market readiness.

Unlike classical grant schemes, the PCP approach adopted by NCBR was structured as a competitive, multi-stage R&D procurement process, aimed at identifying, developing, and validating breakthrough system solutions rather than financing predefined technologies.

Stage 0 – Concept competition

Following the market dialogue, an open competitive call was launched for all eligible market participants, including individual companies and consortia. The objective was to propose the best possible concept for a district heating system capable of delivering at least 80% of its heat from renewable energy sources, without the use of biomass combustion. No specific technologies were preferred or excluded, apart from this constraint.

The competition criteria were designed to be as objective as possible and included:

- Maximum achievable renewable energy share (minimum threshold: 80%)
- Scale of the demonstrator and number of end-users supplied
- Ability to supply both space heating and domestic hot water
- Separation of the demonstrator network from the existing DH system
- Quantitative performance assessment using predefined numerical simulation tools

A key outcome of this stage was the decision to impose a **uniform numerical modelling framework**, including a predefined list of allowable system components. Any deviation from this list required explicit approval and technical justification accepted by NCBR. This approach significantly increased the objectivity and comparability of submitted concepts.

Stage 1 – Concept development and validation

Up to ten participants could enter Stage 1. Ultimately, eight entities submitted proposals, including Euros Energy. Each selected participant received limited funding and a period of six months to further develop their concept. This phase included detailed numerical simulations, technical optimisation, feasibility study and possibly formal preparation to the investment.

Evaluation at this stage was primarily quantitative, based on measurable performance indicators derived from simulations. Qualitative assessment played a secondary role. In parallel, all participants were required to prepare public analytical reports containing recommendations for the future modernisation of district heating in Poland, which remain publicly available through NCBR.

At the end of Stage 1, one concept was selected for implementation. The proposal submitted by Euros Energy achieved the highest overall score and advanced to Stage 2.

Stage 2 – Construction and commissioning

Stage 2 covered the full construction and commissioning of the demonstrator installation. NCBR financed 100% of the eligible investment costs, amounting to 39 511 806.10 Polish zloty net. The installation was commissioned in partial operation in November 2023, with full-scale operation achieved on 29 May 2024.

Stage 3 – Operational evaluation

From 2024 onwards, the project entered the evaluation phase conducted by NCBR. This stage involves continuous operational monitoring, performance measurement, and verification of compliance with the original project assumptions. At the end of the evaluation period in May 2025, Euros Energy submitted updated numerical models calibrated against real measured data. The comparison between simulated and actual performance allowed NCBR to close the evaluation phase with a positive outcome.

- **Ownership structure and operational handover**

Following the completion of the demonstrator phase and evaluation, the installation was transferred to the local district heating operator **Veolia Pólnoc**, which now owns the system as part of the district heating network in Lidzbark Warmiński. Euros Energy serves as an operator of this installation. This handover marked the transition from a publicly funded R&D demonstrator to a fully operational commercial asset embedded in an existing district heating system.

- **Structural limitations of the Polish financing model for PTES**

While the Lidzbark Warmiński demonstrator represents a successful example of large-scale public funding for innovative thermal storage and renewable heating systems, it also highlights several structural limitations of the Polish financing framework for PTES deployment.

First, large-scale thermal energy storage is currently not eligible as a standalone investment under most national support schemes. Storage can only be financed as an auxiliary component of a heat generation investment, which limits the development of system-oriented storage solutions optimised at network level.

Second, the Polish district heating sector operates under a regulated tariff regime based on a cost-plus methodology, supervised by the Energy Regulatory Office. This framework constrains the ability of operators

to monetise system-level benefits such as flexibility, peak shaving, or renewable integration provided by PTES. As a result, business cases for storage remain difficult to justify without very high grant intensities.

Third, public aid intensity is constrained by state aid rules (GBER), typically limiting support to 45% of eligible costs for renewable heat investments for large enterprises. Fully grant-funded demonstrators such as Lidzbark Warmiński are therefore exceptional and not replicable at scale under standard programmes.

Finally, access to funding requires extensive administrative preparation, including feasibility studies, detailed financial models, durability commitments, and long permitting timelines. This significantly increases transaction costs and limits participation primarily to experienced actors capable of managing complex funding procedures.

As a consequence, while the Polish PCP-based model has proven effective for technology validation and first-of-a-kind demonstrations, it does not yet provide a scalable financing pathway for widespread PTES deployment. Future replication will require dedicated support schemes for large-scale thermal storage, improved recognition of system benefits within tariff regulation, and financing instruments enabling partial risk-sharing rather than full grant dependency.

5. Conclusion

This document has presented an overview of financing options and organisational setups for PTES projects. It shows that PTES projects can rely on a broad range of financing instruments, including equity and debt financing as well as subsidies from national and European programs. Access to these instruments strongly depends on the organisational structure of the project owner. Public project owners typically benefit from concessional financing conditions and higher debt capacity, whereas private developers face more restrictive lending terms and often require additional support mechanisms to achieve bankability.

The assessment of ownership structures and business models further highlights that no single approach is universally applicable or directly replicable. Each model presents specific advantages and limitations in terms of risk allocation, administrative complexity, flexibility and alignment with policy objectives. Consequently, selecting appropriate ownership and financing structure is key for the successful implementation of PTES projects and must be addressed alongside technical design considerations from the earliest project stages.

The case studies and experience exchange among the demonstrators illustrate how these principles are applied differently across countries and how financing solutions vary depending on the role and nature of the project owner.

In conclusion, this document provides practical guidance for addressing financing and organisational challenges related to PTES projects. By clarifying available options at an early stage, it contributes to reducing investment risk, strengthening business cases and facilitating the replication and scaling up of PTES solutions across Europe.

6. Appendix

6.1 Program of Workshop 2.2 : Financing and Organisation¹⁴

Part I General presentation of possible financing structures based on organizational structures	9:00 – 9:15	Welcome and presentation of workshop agenda. <i>Newheat</i>
	9:15 – 10:00	How to finance a PTES Project based on your organizational structure? <i>Newheat – Alice Causse</i>
Part II Presentation of the available subsidies in each demonstrator's country	10:00 – 10:30	EU Financing for DHC and large scale seasonal thermal storage. <i>Euroheat & Power – Martin Stroleny</i>
	10:30 – 10:45	Break
	10:45 – 11:00	Subsidies available in France. <i>Newheat – Claire Dutilleul</i>
	11:00 – 11:15	Subsidies available in Denmark and Nordic Financing Solutions. <i>PlanEnergi – Romain Suche</i>
	11:15 – 11:30	Subsidies available in Germany. <i>Rostock – Annika Burckhardt</i>
	11:30 – 11:45	National subsidy schemes and funding for PTES in Austria. <i>Energie Institut – Anja Gahleitner</i>
	11:45 – 12:00	Subsidies available in Poland. <i>SEC – Lilli Wolny</i>
Part III Case Studies : Presentation of the financing structure of the most advanced demonstrators	12:00 – 13:00	Lunch Break
	13:00 – 13:30	Case Study 1 : Financing of Høje Taastrup, Organisation, Operation and Financing of the PTES in Høje Taastrup. <i>PlanEnergi – Per Alex Sørensen</i> District Heating Financing in Denmark - <i>KommuneKredit. PlanEnergi – Per Alex Sørensen</i>
	13:30 – 13:45	Case Study 2 : Financing of Hechingen. <i>Solites – Michael Klock</i>
	13:45 – 14:00	Buffer / Q&A on Case Studies
	14:00	End of workshop

¹⁴ Workshop 2.2 took place online the 11th of November 2024

